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A phenomenological commentary

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Kaarlo Tuori on legal positivism and modern state law

A phenomenological commentary

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1 Introduction

- 1 Kaarlo Tuori's *Advanced Introduction to Legal Positivism (AILP)* offers a particularly insightful engagement with Legal Positivism.¹ The book is organized as a presentation and critical analysis of the key theses that define Legal Positivism as a philosophical approach to law: the irreducibility of legal normativity to social facts, the dependence of law on social sources and law's social efficaciousness, and law and morality as separate and distinct modes of normativity. *AILP* clearly lays out how Legal Positivism's two "Grand Masters," Hans Kelsen and H.L.A. Hart, and their epi- and epi-epigones, develop these theses, while also highlighting differences between them. In so doing, Tuori succeeds in steering clear of the tedious, ever more sterile and irrelevant nitpicking that characterizes much, perhaps most, of the contemporary intramural debate in Legal Positivism, especially in its Hartian ramifications. This, on its own, is already a significant achievement, but the book does much more than that. As the author himself points out, his aim is to critique each of those three theses. The critique is devastating and compelling, all the more so because his presentation of Legal Positivism is evenhanded and well-informed. The closing passage of the book leaves the reader – this reader, at any rate – in no doubt that a renewal of Legal Positivism demands so drastically reconfiguring its basic theses that one must ask: "after such a renewal, in what sense could it still be called 'legal positivism'?"²
- 2 It is thus unsurprising that the title of the book's last chapter, "Beyond legal positivism" echoes the subtitle of Tuori's recent book, *Properties of Law: Modern Law and After*.³ I daresay that *AILP* is also an advanced introduction to Tuori's concept of modern state law, as laid out in *Properties of Law*.⁴ Indeed, this book's reconstruction of the structure of modern state law offers a full-blown formulation of the critical perspective

he brings to bear on Legal Positivism, which *AILP* takes up again in an abridged form. As he perceptively points out, “Legal Positivism itself forms part of modern state law”.⁵ The core of Tuori’s critique, as set out in both books, is that by focusing exclusively on the “surface-level” normativity of legal order, Legal Positivism elides the subsurface, legal-cultural levels, in the absence of which modern state law cannot sustain itself as a distinctive normative order. As he tersely puts it: “law is reduced to its normative aspect and, secondly, the normative aspect is reduced to its surface level.”⁶ *AILP* develops this thesis at considerable length by distinguishing and interconnecting three dimensions or “modes of existence” of modern state law: norms, sociolegal practices, and social practices. It systematically develops each of these in debate with Legal Positivism. Importantly, Tuori devotes the bulk of his analysis to modern *state* law, only briefly discussing emergent legal orders that both draw on and move beyond it and point to the existence of religious and indigenous law. In so doing, he explicitly distances himself from the universalizing, a-historical pretention of Legal Positivism and forcefully questions whether such a pretention is at all possible or even meaningful.

- 3 I am largely in agreement with Tuori’s depiction of Legal Positivism and its problems, and I have little or nothing to comment about on that score. Instead, I want to carry forward the conversation he and I have engaged in about legal phenomenology’s contribution to a theory of legal order. While Tuori is prepared to incorporate certain aspects of legal phenomenology into his theory of modern state law, he is critical about what he takes to be its reductive approach thereto, in particular, the legal phenomenology espoused in my earlier work.⁷ In the first part of what follows, I outline where I take Tuori’s critique to be correct. In the second part, I invert the analysis, arguing that legal phenomenology exposes shortcomings in his model of modern state law and opens avenues for further discussion about convergences and divergences between our approaches to legal order – more precisely, to legal ordering, in the gerundial.

2 *Lebenswelt* and legal *sonderwelten*

- 4 According to Tuori,
- [i]t is the merit of legal phenomenologists to have brought in the first-person viewpoint of individual and collective social actors, and to have attempted to conceptualize how law functions and is perceived to function in sociolegal practices. Yet to declare these the primordial mode of existence *tout court* does not give credit to law’s complicated perspectivism.⁸
- 5 In terms of Tuori’s tripartite structure of modern state law, a phenomenological approach to legal order elides the perspective of legal actors in the narrow sense, namely, of legal professionals who are “the primary subjects of specialized legal practices.”⁹ When addressing legal issues, legal professionals apply a specifically legal *Vorverständnis*, different to that of social actors who participate in what he calls “first-order sociolegal practices.”¹⁰ The former comprises expert legal knowledge, which includes specialized knowledge of the law and its institutional workings, which is rendered partially explicit when dealing with a legal task. It is “partially explicit,” because “the rest remain[s] in a tacit, practical state.”¹¹ By contrast, social actors who engage in general “lifeworld practices” typically participate within “an undifferentiated normative cultural horizon ... which mainly unfolds its effects

unconsciously.”¹² At stake, therefore is a “tacit, practical knowledge and undifferentiated *Vorverständnis*.”¹³

- 6 These preliminary comments on *Vorverständnis*, the lifeworld, and tacit/explicit knowledge suggest that Tuori’s claim that phenomenology’s contribution to a theory of modern state law is circumscribed to a clarification of lifeworld practices, is misleading. The aforementioned notions are phenomenological through and through. Moreover, they are an essential component of the conceptual and methodological framework governing Tuori’s account of modern state law. In particular, the notion of *Vorverständnis* operates in Tuori’s work, as it does with other legal theorists, as one of the constitutive elements of (legal) interpretation. This insight lies at the heart of Gadamer’s philosophical hermeneutics, even if Gadamer refers to *Vorurteil*, *Vorentwurf*, and *Vormeinung*, rather than to *Vorverständnis*.¹⁴ Indeed, if Kelsen (and Tuori) can refer to legal norms as “schemes of interpretation,” Gadamer inaugurates a more radical and general approach to interpretation, suggesting that language “schematizes” or “mediates” our access to the world.¹⁵ For Gadamer, legal interpretation is a specific instance of the general achievement of interpretation, namely, “understand[ing] something as something.”¹⁶ Thus, reality is not given directly but as this or as that. Activities so disparate as science, art, religion, and law are all interpretative in this fundamental sense. In turn, Gadamer’s characterization of understanding invokes Heidegger’s formulation, “something as something,” itself a highly abridged formulation of *intentionality*, the central concept of phenomenology: the appearance of something as something to someone within a world pre-given and co-given with what appears.¹⁷ Tuori therefore unsurprisingly refers to both social and sociolegal modes of *Vorverständnis*. Although Tuori does not say so, both social and sociolegal practices deploy an intentional dynamic: both are manifestations of what Merleau-Ponty describes as *être-au-monde* – being-towards-the-world.¹⁸ Tuori’s further references to “relevance” structures, to the “sedimentation” of surface legal phenomena in law’s subsurface levels, together with the attendant (hermeneutic) circularity between the discursive and tacit dimensions of law, further buttress my claim that Tuori’s debt to phenomenology is far greater than the narrowly circumscribed role he assigns to it in the conceptual economy of both books.
- 7 By these lights, Tuori’s critique of phenomenological approaches to legal order is not, as he would have it, that they are phenomenological.¹⁹ Rather, they are *insufficiently* phenomenological insofar as they elide the legal expert’s experience of law, namely of the legal profession as a specific orientation towards and engagement with the world, irreducible to the worldly orientation of social actors in their everyday life. The critique is spot-on, as far as modern state law is concerned, and demands that phenomenology, particularly my own work, embrace an account of its more “complicated perspectivism,” as he puts it. Thus, his critique of legal phenomenology is not external to, but rather is *internal* to legal phenomenology itself. For his insistence that the perspective of legal actors is irreducible to that of social actors is a late echo of the distinction Husserl introduces between the lifeworld (*Lebenswelt*) and “particular” worlds (*Sonderwelten*), most famously when arguing, in his late work, that the mathematical-technical methods of modern science create an idealized and reified account of nature forgetful of its origins in and dependence on lifeworld experience.²⁰
- 8 Taking Tuori’s insight forward, there is a parallel between the scientific and the juridical *Sonderwelten*. The scientific experiment is a late variation on what Husserl

describes as the “idealization” of nature exemplified by Galileo, who constructed pure geometrical figures not found in concrete experience, but which are possible because these figures are commensurate with it. Lawmaking, too, involves a certain idealization, namely the *juridification* of reality: the real is disclosed by way of the distinction between legal subjects and the object of the legal rights and obligations through which legal subjects stand in relation to each other. Science, through its idealization of the lifeworld, substitutes a mathematical manifold for the “plena” of intuitive experience.²¹ Law, through its juridification of the lifeworld, substitutes a lattice of legal subject/object relations for the manifold of social relations in all their variegated manifestations. To be in modern law is to be juridified as a legal subject, or as the object of relations between legal subjects. In a non-trivial sense, a collective becomes a *legal* collective through juridification. Modern state lawmaking works *within* and *on* the boundaries of authoritatively *and professionally* mediated collective action, which stands at a considerable distance from everyday experience in the lifeworld. Here, precisely, is where contemporary sociolegal critiques of the “juridification” of sociality find their point of entry, an issue that would have merited attention in Tuori’s exposé.

3 A phenomenological critique of Tuori’s account of legal normativity

- 9 So much for, at least for the purposes of this commentary, how Tuori rightly highlights lacunae in legal phenomenology on modern state law and Legal Positivism. But how, inversely, might legal phenomenology bring its conceptual and normative resources to bear on Tuori’s account of modern state law? Specifically, how might the core phenomenological concept of intentionality both critique and contribute to Tuori’s account of modern state law and Legal Positivism? Given the limited space allowed for this commentary, I can do no more here than engage with Tuori by way of more or less *staccato* theses, referring the reader to my other work for an extended justification of these theses.
- 10 **Thesis 1 (*The ubiquity of legal intentionality*).** The intentional dynamic of lawmaking is not limited to “interpretative” activities in the sense Tuori indicates: it is constitutive for *all* lawmaking. On a phenomenological reading of collective action, lawmaking comprises both social and sociolegal practices, regardless of whether or not those practices understand themselves explicitly as such. Indeed, the disclosure of something as having this or that legal meaning within a pre-given and co-given world is operative across all specifically authorized modalities of lawmaking by modern states, including legislation, international treaties, constitutional enactments, executive decisions, judicial rulings, contracts, testaments, and so forth. So, too, doctrinal contributions and interventions by legal experts when interpreting state law. Moreover, intentionality is by no means limited to second order “interpretative” legal practices, as Tuori seems to suggest: first-order, social practices by individuals and groups in the course of their everyday lifeworld activities are no less intentional and no less modes of lawmaking than the former, insofar as they actualize the legal norms of a collective. Tuori would have done well to engage directly with phenomenological studies on the structure and dynamic of intentionality to ground the differences and relations between social and sociolegal practices as integral dimensions of lawmaking in modern states.²²

- 11 **Thesis 2 (*The politics of lawmaking*)**. Acknowledging the constitutive role of intentionality for all of lawmaking highlights the dearth of concrete reflections about *politics* in Tuori's account of modern state law and Legal Positivism. To be sure, he acknowledges the importance of politics in making sense of modern state law, such as when critiquing Kelsen's sharp distinction between legal theory and social policy and when noting that "[i]n Hartian analytical positivism, law's isolation from politics and ideology is even more hermetic."²³ Yet the task for an account of modern state law alternative to Legal Positivism is to show how the structure and dynamic of *lawmaking itself* is irreducibly political – *because* it is lawmaking. Here, both books fall far short of providing adequate analysis. It is not enough to insist on the need for "acceptance" of the legal order by social actors and, at least partially, by legal actors. Evincing the constitutively political character of social and sociolegal practices demands showing how representation and recognition inform state lawmaking since these are modes of intentionality that articulate the politics of lawmaking that plays out in modern state law – including "legal interpretation." A phenomenological contribution to Tuori's insistence on the need to reclaim politics for a theory of modern state law consists in highlighting the representational and recognitive dynamic that plays out in lawmaking. More precisely, if, as Tuori and I agree, social and sociolegal practices involve the first-person plural perspective of "we," then representation and recognition are the privileged modes by which claims to *commonality* are raised and contested about action qua *collective* action. A fortiori, such claims and contestations are at stake in *all* "interpretative" practices, as described by Tuori.
- 12 **Thesis 3 (*The inclusive/exclusive dynamic of lawmaking*)**. That lawmaking always involves claims and counterclaims about commonality entails that it cannot include without excluding. As Jullien points out, "if the common is what I share with others, it is also, due to this fact and following this dividing line (which stands as a line of demarcation), that which excludes all others."²⁴ Although Tuori discusses identity/difference and unity/plurality in modern state law, his analysis fails to adequately address how these are systematically related to the dynamic of inclusion/exclusion. The locus of those three conceptual pairs is the intentional "as" deployed in lawmaking. Something is disclosed as having this, *rather than that* legal meaning, giving rise to significative, representational, and recognitive differences between the intention and the intended.²⁵ Indeed, the processes of collective self-identification that take place through lawmaking, whether in sociolegal or social practices, are always also processes of collective self-differentiation. That lawmaking is intentional means that "we" *are more and other than how we signify ourselves*. So, too, unity and plurality: collective self-unification is always a self-pluralization. As a process of social integration, lawmaking is coevally a process of social disintegration *because* it purports to be integrative, that is, because it claims to determine the point of collective action "we" are deemed to hold in common. Finally, the processes of what Ricœur calls self-recognition and recognition of the other, whereby a collective affirms itself in existence in the course of struggles for recognition, are always also, to a greater or lesser extent, processes of collective self- and other-misrecognition: "not in our name!"²⁶ Finally, and crucially, the intentionality of all lawmaking gives rise to a *normative difference* that emerges in the very process of articulating what counts as legal or illegal. What appears is more and other than the *value* with which it appears to "us," the collective, when authoritatively disclosed with this or that legal meaning.²⁷ Here again, Tuori's move to contain a phenomenological contribution to its thematization of

lifeworld practices passes by an opportunity to critically sharpen an account of the structure and political dynamic of lawmaking in all its variations.

13 **Thesis 4 (Positivity, contingency, and modernity).** Fully embracing the dynamic of inclusion and exclusion called forth by the intentional structure of lawmaking would contribute to thematizing the concept of order underpinning modern state law. In particular, this dynamic would give concrete content to “determination,” the mechanism through which lawmaking orders. This topic remains largely implicit in Tuori’s engagement with Kelsen and Hart, and in his own account of modern state law. In this context, Cassirer refers to determination or limitation as the general function of order: “The pure *function* of the concept of order is one and the same, no matter on which particular matter and within which special area of the mind it is effective. Generally speaking, it is always a matter of limiting the unlimited, of determining the relatively indeterminate.”²⁸ To determine or limit, in the phenomenological sense of intending something *as this or as that*, is to order social life. And to do so is to include and exclude from a world. Crucially, this characterization of ordering is quintessentially *modern*. It is not enough for Tuori to hold, concurring *in this* with Legal Positivism, that “positive law is posited law which results from human action.”²⁹ At stake is the experience of the radical contingency of order, including legal order, characteristic of modernity. This experience obtains concrete expression in an ambiguity hidden in the notion of positive law. On the one hand, law is positive inasmuch as it is posited law, that is, the outcome of human agency. On the other hand, it is contingent. In the face of this ambiguity, the urgent question confronting modern theories of lawmaking concerns the ground of law, a question that must be addressed by way of an inquiry into the act of the positing of law. The phenomenological contribution to a theory of the modernity of modern law is to have identified the systematic link between these two dimensions of the positivity of lawmaking. In effect, the residual groundlessness of the dynamic of inclusion and exclusion operative in legal intentionality reveals lawmaking as *irreducibly contingent*, even if not necessarily arbitrary.³⁰ Here again, phenomenology would have been of service to articulate the unthematized presupposition about positive law governing Tuori’s methodological move to view modern state law as “an ideal type in Max Weber’s sense, generalized from tokens, enhancing some of their features and downplaying others, consciously or unconsciously.”³¹

14 **Thesis 5 (The primordality of lifeworld practices).** As mentioned, Tuori is entirely correct in pointing out that earlier contributions to a legal phenomenology, including mine, neglect an account of the specificity of legal practices and the legal *Sonderwelt* within which they are situated. While welcoming this important correction to a phenomenological approach to legal order, Husserl’s phenomenological genealogy of the scientific *Sonderwelt* suggests, contra Tuori, that there is a sense in which lifeworld practices are *primordial* with respect to sociolegal practices. For a legal *Sonderwelt*, no less than a scientific *Sonderwelt*, cannot be fully autonomous with respect to the lifeworld; it not only emerges from the *Lebenswelt* but also *depends* on it for its transformation by way of lifeworld events and situations that call into question the boundaries of what counts as legal and illegal. The “double citizenship” to which Tuori refers when characterizing legal experts presupposes their participation in lifeworld practices in the absence of which there could be, strictly speaking, no “social sources” of law. This is not to say that phenomenology views the lifeworld as primordial “*tout court*,” as Tuori incorrectly suggests. Husserl was at pains to show that if science is an

idealization of lifeworld practices, these are, in turn, permeated by its idealizations. I, too, point to this circularity with respect to law in *Fault Lines of Globalization*.³²

- 15 **Thesis 6 (Legal responsivity).** Although Tuori insists time and again on the crucial role of principles of law in connecting sociolegal practices to social practices, the invocation of these principles *arrives too late* if we are to make sense of the emergence of legal normativity. Such principles are legal *responses* to a lifeworld experience of what, to a greater or lesser extent, challenges what a legal order has qualified as (il)legal behavior or situations. *The lifeworld challenge or question comes before a legal response*, and that challenge or question can only be experienced as such and give rise to a legal response, whatever its content, if the legal expert participates in lifeworld practices and the normative expectations to which it gives rise. Legal modes of *Vorverständnis* continue to rely on social modes thereof if they are to disclose what appears as legal or illegal, as is clear from “open legal concepts” and, more generally, the lifeworld contextuality of legal language. Along these lines, I view Tuori’s reference to “extraordinary” events and situations as a tacit acknowledgment of the phenomenological insight that legal intentionality has a *responsive* structure, hence that, in this sense, lifeworld practices are primordial.³³ This phenomenological insight impinges directly on collective action theory in its various contemporary presentations by authors such as Bratman, Pettit, Tuomela, and Gilbert: *collective action begins as collective passion*.³⁴
- 16 **Thesis 7 (The double asymmetry of struggles for recognition).** The responsive intentionality at work in lawmaking points to a *double asymmetry* that plays out in struggles for legal recognition in modern state law. On the one hand, a demand for recognition is asymmetrical with respect to a collective’s legal response because it is not merely a claim to inclusion in relations of legal reciprocity as a way of redressing the violation of the Other’s identity/difference. Demands for recognition are to a greater or lesser extent *in excess* of the possibilities available to the group perspective opened up by the point of collective action. On the other hand, the legal response governed by that group perspective is asymmetrical with respect to the question because it *frames* the demand in ways that render it amenable to a response in the terms of (transformed) relations of reciprocity available to joint action. Collectives frame their legal responses to demands for recognition in such a way that they can recognize *themselves* when transforming what counts as collective action with a view to recognizing the Other (in themselves). There is always at least a minimal gap between the question to which a legal collective responds – e.g., What is/ought *our* joint action to be about? – and the question addressed to it by a demand for recognition. I suggest, against universalizing interpretations of authority and legitimacy, that the phenomenological concept of lawmaking enjoins viewing lawmaking as a process of unification *without* totalization, not, as in Habermas *cum suis*, of unification *as* totalization. This is a thesis I think Tuori would be prepared to embrace, and if so, it confirms that legal phenomenology can contribute to Tuori’s theory of modern state law in more – and more fundamental – ways than he has envisaged.
- 17 **Thesis 8 (Norms, normality, and normativity).** This thesis engages with Tuori’s elegant critique of the three theses that underpin Legal Positivism, the third of which – the separability thesis – is a corollary of the first two: the irreducibility of legal normativity to social facts and the dependence of law on social sources and the social efficaciousness of law. He compellingly shows that these theses summarize Legal Positivism’s unsuccessful attempt to deal with the problem of connecting “ought” to

“is,” that is, norms to facts, without collapsing one into the other. Tuori’s alternative is to hold that “law also includes a legal-cultural level and that morally laden principles constitute an integral element of legal culture ...”³⁵ In brief, “the most fatal lack in legal positivism’s understanding of legal normativity is the absence of general legal principles.”³⁶

- 18 This very Dworkinian approach to general legal principles, even when supplemented with a Gadamerian approach to legal interpretation, cannot address the problem of the *genesis* of legal normativity bequeathed by Legal Positivism, since legal principles already presuppose the existence of legal normativity. Here I Tuori could have provided a more charitable interpretation of Kelsen’s *Pure Theory of Law*, though he does offer an acute critique of the limitations of Kelsen’s *Grundnorm*. Most importantly in Kelsen’s uncompromising radicality, is to have exposed with all clarity that the *emergence of legal normativity* is the key problem confronting legal theory, even if the *Grundnorm* fails in this task. No less importantly, Kelsen’s nomodynamics has the great advantage of recognizing that a theory of the emergence of legal normativity must take place as a *genealogical* inquiry because we are always already *within* normativity. However valuable in its own right, the invocation of legal practices cannot substitute for a genealogy of legal normativity.
- 19 A genealogical inquiry that offers a more fruitful approach to the tension and connection between “is” and “ought” takes its point of departure in a phenomenological motif that runs through Tuori’s account of lawmaking, yet which remains unexplored as properly genealogical in both books. Indeed, at one point he refers to “extraordinary” situations and events that call forth a legal response, whether by state authorities or by legal professionals.³⁷ Indeed, the extraordinary evokes the connection between *norms, normality, and normativity*, a phenomenological theme leading back at least as far as Husserl’s *Ideas II*, and indirectly raised by Tuori when referring to habits, social efficacy, and tacit knowledge.³⁸
- 20 A phenomenological genealogy of legal normativity begins by recognizing that the intentional directedness of an “ought” towards an “is” has the form of an anticipation about what ought to appear and how it ought to appear. As long as something is what it ought to be in the course of practical involvement with the world, the norm that holds sway in our worldly involvement remains unthematic. Its hold on the real, its capacity to anticipate what will appear and how it will appear, is confirmed, such that something ought to be what it is. This is the relationship between “ought” and “is” that plays out in *normality*, namely, the experience in which what is, is as it ought to be, and conversely, what ought to be, is what is. What Tuori calls the “extraordinary” is a deviation from normality in which the norm of normality becomes thematic in the mode of its negation, depriving habitual behaviour of its unquestioned status and showing it to be a more or less contingent mode of worldly involvement.³⁹ Call it *abnormality* and, in a legal mode, *a-legality*.⁴⁰ Lawmaking is a response to the experience of abnormality that confronts us with the question about what we aim at, i.e., about what our agency, individual and collective, ought to be about. This is phenomenology’s response to the problem of connecting “is” and “ought,” while also holding them separate. In a word, Hume’s guillotine is emergent. A further development of this phenomenological insight can only be undertaken if lawmaking is acknowledged to be *bodily* lawmaking, that is, that norms are first and foremost *embodied norms* and reason, *embodied* reason.⁴¹ Here again, phenomenology could have been of help in addressing

the impasses of Legal Positivism that Tuori so masterfully has exposed in *AILP and Properties of Law*.

- 21 I look forward to Kalle's reply and, beyond that, to further exploring convergences and divergences between our approaches to the concept of legal order.

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NOTES

1. Tuori 2025.
2. Tuori 2025: 158.
3. Tuori 2021.
4. Tuori 2021.
5. Tuori 2021: 3.
6. Tuori 2021: 3.
7. Lindahl 2013; Lindahl 2018.
8. Tuori 2021: 8.
9. Tuori 2021: 8.
10. Tuori 2021: 8.
11. Tuori 2021: 8.
12. Tuori 2021: 8.
13. Tuori 2021: 8.
14. As pointed out by Gizbert-Studnicki, who adds that the concept of a hermeneutic circle has been “widely adopted by a hermeneutically oriented philosophy of law, even if variously interpreted.” Gizbert-Studnicki 1987: 481.
15. Kelsen 1982: 8; Gadamer 1989: 28–9.
16. Gadamer 1989: 30.
17. Heidegger 1962: §32.
18. Merleau-Ponty 2012.
19. Tuori 2021.
20. Husserl 1970. “For Husserl, a *Sonderwelt* is a separate realm that is constituted and closed off by a specific purpose or a guiding purposive idea—regardless of whether it is a practical or theoretical purpose, an individual or a communal purpose” (Marx 1970: 63).
21. Husserl 1970: 33.
22. See Waldenfels 1994; Waldenfels 2002; Steinbock 1995; Menga 2018.
23. Tuori 2025: 154–5.
24. Jullien 2014: 21.
25. Waldenfels 1980; Waldenfels 2002.
26. Ricoeur 2007; García Düttmann 2000.
27. Lindahl 2025a.
28. Cassirer 1985: 100.

29. Tuori 2025: 2.
 30. See Blumenberg 1983 and Blumenberg 1986 on modernity's radical contingency.
 31. Tuori 2021: 30.
 32. Lindahl 2013.
 33. Tuori 2021: 23.
 34. See Waldenfels 1994 for an extended account of responsive intentionality.
 35. Tuori 2025: 157.
 36. Tuori 2025: 156.
 37. Tuori 2021: 23.
 38. Husserl 1989.
 39. Lindahl 2025b.
 40. Although Tuori refers in passing to a-legality in *Properties of Law*, he does so in ways that are surprisingly misguided. I leave a discussion of this misreading, and of the attendant paradoxes of a-legality and constituent power, for another occasion.
 41. For a full-blown phenomenology of the emergence of legal normativity in relation to the embodiment of norms, normality, and normativity see Lindahl 2025b.
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ABSTRACTS

This paper offers a phenomenologically informed commentary on Kaarlo Tuori's recent book, *Advanced Introduction to Legal Positivism*. On the one hand, it provides support for Tuori's critical engagement with a phenomenology of legal ordering. On the other hand, it brings conceptual and normative resources of phenomenology to bear on Tuori's recent work, exposing some of its shortcomings and missed opportunities for drawing on a phenomenology of legal order to strengthen his model of modern state law.

Kaarlo Tuori o pravnem pozitivizmu in modernem državnem pravu. Fenomenološki komentar. Ta članek ponuja fenomenološko utemeljen komentar k nedavni knjigi Kaarla Tuorija *Advanced Introduction to Legal Positivism*. Po eni strani podpira Tuorijevo kritično soočenje s fenomenologijo pravnega urejanja. Po drugi strani pa na njegovo nedavno delo aplicira pojmovne in normativne vire fenomenologije ter razkriva nekatere njegove pomanjkljivosti in zamujene priložnosti za uporabo fenomenologije pravnega reda pri krepitvi njegovega modela modernega državnega prava.

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motsclessl Pravni pozitivizem, odzivna intencionalnost, življenjski svet, vključevanje/
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